

THE BIOSTRATIGRAPHY AND PALEOENVIRONMENT STUDIES OF MAMU, AJALI, AND NSUKKA FORMATIONS, ANAMBRA BASIN, OUTCROPPED AT IHUBE, IMO STATE, SOUTHEASTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: Biostratigraphy and paleoenvironment of deposition studies were carried out on the Mamu, Ajali, and Nsukka Formations of Anambra Basin, Southeastern Nigeria. The outcrops are located at Ihube and Uturu. The three lithologic units include: Unit A, bluish-brown sandy-shale which is the Mamu Formation; Unit B, whitish friable sandstone which is the Ajali Sandstone; and Unit C, brownish lateritic sandy-shale which is the Nsukka Formation. The result of grain-size distribution analysis carried out on the samples collected from unit B showed that the unit was deposited in a fluvial environment. The area shows a moderately well sorted to poorly sorted unit and lack of carbonate cement and thus a continental origin is suggested. Also the area shows a fining upward sequence and this indicates a transgressive phase and suggests the depositional environment to be a fluvial continental environment. The unimodal paleocurrent pattern with a mean vector azimuth of 244⁰ indicates a Southwesternly direction and provenance probably from the Benue Trough. The results of the bio-stratigraphical analysis carried out on the shale samples showed that unit A is of Lower-Upper Maastrichtian age, on the basis of the following age diagnostic palynomorphs species such as *Cretacaeiporitescabratus*, *Cretacaeisporitesmulleri*, *Droseriditessenonicus*, *Monocolpopollenitessphaeroidites*, *Tricolporopollenites* sp. SCI. 141, *Ephedripites* sp., *Galaecorneaclavis* and *Tricolporopollenites* sp. and unit C is of Upper-Maastrichtian age, with the following index species: *Longapertitesmarginatus*, *Spinizonocolpitesbaculatus*, *Retidiporitesmagdalenensis*, *Buttineaandreevi*, *Echitriporitestrianguliformis*, *Longapertitesmicrofoveolatus*, *Rugulatisporitescaperatus*, *Gleicheniditessenonicus* and *Monocolpitesmarginatus*. Its depositional environment indicated shallow marine for unit A, because of the presence of marine micro-plankton such as, *Spiniferites* sp. and *Oligosphaeridium* complex, with corresponding absence of *Longapertites marginatus* and *Spinizonocolpites baculatus*, and mangrove swampy environment for unit C, because of the preponderance occurrence of *Longapertites marginatus* and *Spinizonocolpites baculatus* species, along with *Laevigatosporitesovatus*.

Keywords: Biostratigraphy, Paleoenvironment, Lithology, Azimuth, Index Fossils, Grain-size, Geologic map.

INTRODUCTION

Location, Extent and Accessibility

The study area is Ihuba which is commonly called Aku-Ihuba, located in Imo State, Southeastern Nigeria and covers other areas like, Obiohia, Okigwe, Leru (in Abia State), Nduhu, Umuanyi, Umulolo, Ubaha and Ugwuella-Uturu all in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State. The study area lies between latitudes 5°50'N and 5°55'N, and longitudes 7°20'E and 7°25'E. The area extent is about 85.6km².

The study area is accessible through the Enugu-Port-Harcourt express way to Ihuba junction, then through a minor road leading into the villages. Also, a minor road from Ezinna-Isuochi leads to the study area. A network of tarred and untarred minor roads and bush paths helped in location of outcrops and exposures within the study area

Figure 1: The Geologic Map of the Study Area

Table 1: Correlation Chart for Early Cretaceous Tertiary Strata in the South-Eastern Nigeria (Nwajide, 1990).

AGE		SOUTHERN BENUE TROUGH	
NUMERIC	GEOLOGIC	Abakaliki-Anambara Basin	Afikpo Basin
m.y 30	Oligocene	Ogwashi-Asaba Formation	Ogwashi-Asaba Formation
54.9	Eocene	Ameki/Nanka Formation/ Nsugbe Sandstone (Ameki Group)	Ameki Formation
6.5	Palaeocene	Imo Formation Nsukka Formation	Imo Formation Nsukka Formation
73	Maastrichtian	Ajali Formation Mamu Formation	Ajali Formation Mamu Formation
83 87.5	Camparian	Npkoro Oweli Formation/Enugu Shale	Nkporo Shale/ Afikpo Sandstone
	Santonian	Agbani Sndstone/Awgu Shale	Non-deposition/erision
88.5	Coriacian	Eze Aku Grupo	Eze Aku Grupo (incl. Amasiri Sandstone)
	Turonian		
93 100	Cenomanian- Albian	Asu River Group	Asu River Group

STUDY AREA

MATERIALS, METHODS AND RESULTS

Materials

- ❖ Bruton compass – for measuring the attitude and bearing of beds, fractures and faults.
- ❖ Global Positioning System (GPS) – for taking the co-ordinate and elevation of a place.
- ❖ Geologic hammer – for strength properties assessment and sample collection.
- ❖ Camera – for taking photographs of vegetation, outcrops, and quarry sites.
- ❖ Field notebook, ruler, protractor and writing materials - for recording data obtained from the field.
- ❖ Sample bags – for sample collection.
- ❖ Measuring tape – for measuring outcrop thickness and logging of outcrop, and distances of roads in the mapped area.
- ❖ Sieve set – for the sieve analysis.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Sediment logical Analysis

Grain size distribution analysis was carried out on the samples of the Friable Sandstone unit. Samples were collected from different locations in the study area, in order to determine the range of particles in it and the percentage of particles in each of the size between the maximum and the minimum. The samples were dried under

the sun and then disaggregated and sieved for a period of 30 minutes in half phi sieve screen model ASTM using mechanical means. The weight of samples retained on each sieve was obtained at the end. The log probability and cumulative curves were plotted for each of the sample and statistical parameters were deduced using Folk and Ward, (1957) formula with the grain size measured in phi (ϕ). Certain parameters were obtained from the grain distribution, and these parameters include median grain size, mean grain size, sorting, skewness and kurtosis.

Table 2: Verbal Terms and Scale (Folk and Ward, 1957)

Sorting (σ_I)	Skewness (Sk_I)	Kurtosis (K_G)
Very well sorted	< 0.35	Very finely +0.3 to +1.0
Well sorted	0.35 –	skewed +0.1 to +0.3
Moderately well sorted	0.50	Finely +0.1 to -0.1
Moderately sorted	0.50 –	skewed -0.1 to -0.3
Poorly sorted	0.70	Symmetrical -0.3 to -1.0
Very poorly sorted	0.70 –	Coarsely
Extremely poorly sorted	1.00	skewed
	1.00 –	Very coarsely
	2.00	skewed
	2.00 –	
	4.00	
	> 4.00	

Table 3: Results of the Grain Size Distribution.

Sample No	Mean	Median	Sorting	Skewness	Kurtosis
AOE/2018/02	1.3	1.16	1.42	0.05	0.9
AOE/2018/06	0.93	1.21	1.34	-0.25	0.77
AOE/2018/09	1.47	1.24	1.26	0.05	1.0

Figure 2: A plot of percentage cumulative weight against phi for AOE/2018/02.

Figure 3: A plot of percentage cumulative weight against Phi for AOE/2018/06.

Figure 4: A plot of percentage cumulative weight against Phi for AOE/2018/09.

Table 4: Sample Textural Parameter.

Sample No	Mean (Mz)	Sorting (σ^2)	Skewness (Ski)	Kurtosis (Kg)
AOE/2018/02	1.3 Medium grain	1.42 Poorly sorted	0.05 Positive near symmetrical	0.9 Mesokurtic
AOE/2018/06	0.93 Medium grain	1.34 Poorly sorted	-0.25 Negative coarse skewed	0.77 Platykurtic
AOE/2018/09	1.47 Medium grain	1.26 Poorly sorted	0.05 Positive near symmetrical	1.0 Mesokurtic

Bivariate Parameter Results

Figure 5: Bivariate Plot of Skewness against Sorting of the friable sandstone at Ihube, east of Leru junction.

Figure 6: Bivariate Plot of Mean-size against Standard deviation of the friable sandstone at Uturu.

PALYNOLOGICAL ANALYSIS.

Analytical Method and Techniques

The method of study included laboratory sample processing and transmitted light microscopic logging. Three (3) samples from locations 5, 9, and 11 were subjected to palynological sample processing for their palynomorphs. The sample preparation was carried out using the conventional method of acid maceration technique for recovering acid-insoluble organic-walled microfossils from sediments. Each sample was thoroughly cleaned to remove field contaminants. 10g of each sample was weighed out in a standard weighing balance and gently crushed with agate mortar and piston. The crushed sample was digested for 30 minutes in 40% conc. hydrochloric acid for removal of carbonate and 72 hours in 48% conc. hydrofluoric acid to remove silicates. The digested sample was diluted with distil water and sieve-washed through 10 microns nylon mesh. The sieve-washed 10g residues equivalent was partitioned into two parts, 5g each, for oxidation and for kerogen assessment. The 5g residue extracts were oxidized for 30 minutes in 70% conc. HNO₃ and 5 minutes in Schulze solution to render the fossils translucent for transmitted light microscopy. The acid-free oxidized residues were rinsed in 2% conc. KOH solution to neutralize the acid; swirled to remove the resistant coarse mineral particles and undigested organic matter. The swirled residues were collected on the sieve and stained with Safranin – O to increase the depth of contrast for microscopic examination and photography.

The stained residues (aliquots) were dispersed with polyvinyl alcohol, dried on cover-slips and mounted in petro-poxy resin. One slide was made from each sample and logged under the transmitted light microscopy. Light photomicrographs were taken with leicall binocular microscope.

Palynological Result

Table 5: Occurrence and Distributions of the Palynomorphs Counts in the Examined Samples.

SAMPLE NO.	LOC 5 DARK SHALE	LOC 9 GREY SHALE	LOC 11 GREY SHALE
PALYNO MORPHS SPECIES			
POLLEN			
Droseriditessenonicus	1	1	0
Cretacaeiporitescabratus	2	1	0
Cretacaeiporitesmulleri	0	2	0
Monocolpopollenitessphaeroidites	4	2	0
Tricolporopollenites sp. SCI. 141	2	4	0
Monosulcites sp.	5	7	0
Ephedripites sp.	3	2	0
Galaecorneaclavis	2	3	0
Tricolporopollenites sp.	4	2	0
Echitriporitestrianguliformis	0	0	3
Longapertitesmarginatus	0	0	12

Longapertitesmicrofoveolatus	0	0	3
Spinizonocolpitesbaculatus	0	0	2
Retidiporitesmagdalenensis	0	0	1
Buttineaandreevi	0	0	2
Monocolpitesmarginatus	0	0	4
SPORES			
Rugulatisporitescaperatus	0	0	2
Gleicheniditessenonicus	0	0	1
Cyathidites minor	0	0	3
Cingulatisporitesornatus	0	0	1
Leiotriletesadriennis	0	0	2
Laevigatosporitesovatus	2	2	4
MARINE SPECIES			
Dinogymniumeuclaensis	1	1	0
Spiniferites sp.	1	0	1
Subtilisphaera sp.	1	1	0
Cordosphaeridium sp.	0	0	2
Senegalinium sp.	0	0	4
Oligosphaeridium complex	0	1	0

Figure 7: Micrographs of Some Palynomorphs Recovered in the Examined Samples.

Magnification Numbers 2 and 4 (X 100 oil immersion), others (X 40).

1. Longapertitesmarginatus
2. Monocolpitesmarginatus
3. Laevigatosporitesovatus
4. Echitriporitestrianguliformis
5. Spinizonocolpitesbaculatus
6. Buttiniaandreevi
7. Cretacaeiporitescabratus
8. Ephedripites sp.
9. Oligosphaeridium complex

Paleo-environments of Deposition

Table 6: Summary of the Palynomorphs % Frequency Distributions and their Paleoenvironmental Inferences.

SAMPLE NO.	PALYNOMORPHS FREQUENCY			PALEO-SALINITY	PALEOENVIRONMENT S OF DEPOSITION
	Spores	Pollen	Marine Species Dinocysts		
LOC 5 (unit A)	7 %	82 %	11 %	Normal marine	Open marine/ shallow shelf
LOC 9	7 %	83 %	10 %	Normal marine	Open marine/ shallow shelf
LOC 11	28 %	57 %	15 %	Brackish water	Mangrove swamp (estuarine)/ Lower deltaic plain

Table 6 above shows the summary of palynomorphs percentage frequency distributions and their paleo-environmental inferences. The palynomorphs of environmental value encountered in the examined samples included, **Spinizonocolpites baculatus**, **Longapertites marginatus**, **Longapertites microfoveolatus** and **Laevigatosporitesovatus**.

The species of **Spinizonocolpites** and **Longapertites** are well-known pollen of palmae inhabiting similar environment as that of mangrove swamp of the humid tropics, (van der Hammen, 1954, van Hoeken-Klinkenberg, 1964, Muller, 1968, Umeji, 2002, Umeji and Nwajide, 2014, Ikegwuonu and Umeji, 2016). **Laevigatosporitesovatus** is a fern spore of swampy freshwater, (Rull, 1997 and Germeraad et al.1968).

In this study, there was a mixed condition of freshwater (non-brackish) forms in different proportions, with the brackish water/mangrove swamp species in the examined samples. The preponderance occurrence of **Longapertites marginatus** and **Spinizonocolpites baculatus** species, along with **Laevigatosporitesovatus**, in

sample LOC 11, indicate deposition under near shore brackish water/or mangrove swamp environment, (Table 6).

Moreover, the presence of marine micro-plankton such as, **Spiniferites** sp. (open marine) and **Oligosphaeridium complex**, with corresponding absence of **Longapertites marginatus** and **Spinizonocolpites baculatus** (mangrove species), in samples LOC 5 and LOC 9, is indicative of open marine/ shallow shelf depositional environment, (Table 6)

PALEOCURRENT ANALYSIS

The dip and azimuth of sixteen Fore-sets of planner cross beds were measured from the cross bedded friable sandstone units of Ihube and Uturu areas. The measurement were carefully taken and recorded. The measurements were analyzed using variable constraints system by calculating the mean vector Azimuths (MVA) and variables of the cross-bed units of the friable sandstones of Ihube and Uturu areas. In other to determine the paleocurrent direction of this sandstone as well the trend of the paleocurrent, a rose diagram was constructed (See Figure 7) which showed that the direction of flow is from NE towards SW direction.

Table 7: Paleocurrent Analytical Table.

S/N	Azimuth (A)	Dip (D)	Sin (A)	Cos (A)	Cos (D)	(AZ-MVA) ²
1	260 ⁰	34 ⁰	-0.984	-0.173	0.829	256
2	250 ⁰	22 ⁰	-0.939	-0.342	0.927	36
3	200 ⁰	18 ⁰	-0.342	-0.939	0.951	1936
4	340 ⁰	24 ⁰	-0.342	0.939	0.913	9216
5	50 ⁰	20 ⁰	0.7660	0.642	0.939	37636
6	22 ⁰	22 ⁰	0.374	0.927	0.927	49284
7	226 ⁰	14 ⁰	-0.719	-0.694	0.970	324
8	233 ⁰	23 ⁰	-0.798	-0.601	0.920	121
9	230 ⁰	30 ⁰	-0.7760	-0.642	0.866	196
10	140 ⁰	25 ⁰	-0.642	-0.766	0.906	10816
11	120 ⁰	20 ⁰	0.866	-0.5	0.939	15376
12	220 ⁰	40 ⁰	-0.642	-0.7660	0.766	576
13	292 ⁰	14 ⁰	-0.927	0.374	0.970	2304
14	262 ⁰	20 ⁰	-0.990	-0.139	0.939	324
15	340 ⁰	20 ⁰	-0.342	0.939	0.939	9216
16	240 ⁰	30 ⁰	-0.866	-0.5	0.866	16
			Σ=(-4.5993)	Σ=(-2.2419)	Σ=(14.572)	Σ=(137,633)

Mean Vector Azimuth = $\tan^{-1} (\Sigma \sin A) / (\Sigma \cos A)$

Where $\Sigma \sin A = -4.5993$

$$\Sigma \cos A = -2.2419$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Therefore, MVA} &= \tan^{-1} = \frac{-4.5993}{-2.2419} \\ &= 64^\circ \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hence MVA} &= 64^\circ + 180^\circ \\ &= 244^\circ \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Variance} = \Sigma (A_i - \text{MVA})^2 / (N-1)$$

MVA = Computed Mean Vector Azimuth

N = Total Number of outcome (16)

A_i = Azimuth

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{137,633}{16-1} = \frac{137,633}{15} = 9175.533$$

$$\text{Vector Strength} = \frac{\sqrt{\Sigma(\sin A^2) + \Sigma(\cos A^2)}}{N}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Vector Strength} &= \frac{\sqrt{\Sigma(-4.5993)^2 + \Sigma(-2.2419)^2}}{16} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{21.153 - 5.026}}{16} \\ &= \sqrt{1.0079375} = 1.003960906i \end{aligned}$$

Figure 8: Rose Diagram of the Friable Sandstones within the Study Area

DISCUSSION

Discussion of Results

From the result of the sieve analysis above, the area shows a moderately well sorted to poorly sorted unit and lack of carbonate cement and thus a continental origin is suggested. Also the area shows a fining upward sequence and this indicates a transgressive phase and suggests the depositional environment to be a fluvial continental environment as evident in the plots of mean size against standard deviation and skewness against sorting (Figures 4 and 5).

And for Biostratigraphic Age Assessment, Table 4 above shows the occurrence and distribution of the palynomorphs recovered from the examined samples. From the result, the following deductions were made:

1. Samples LOC 5 and LOC 9, were assigned to Lower – Upper Maastrichtian interval, on the basis of the following age diagnostic palynomorphs species such as, *Cretacaeiporitescabratus*, *Cretacaeisporitesmulleri*, *Droseriditessenonicus*, *Monocolpopollenitessphaeroidites*, *Tricolporopollenites* sp. SCI. 141, *Ephedripites* sp., *Galacorneaclavis* and *Tricolporopollenites* sp. (Lawal and Moullade, 1987; Abubakar et al., 2011).
2. Meanwhile, sample LOC 11 was dated Upper-Maastrichtian age, with the following index species: *Longapertitesmarginatus* (in overwhelming abundance), *Spinizonocolpitesbaculatus*,

Retidiporitesmagdalenensis, Buttineaandreevi, Echitriporitestrianguliformis, Longapertitesmicrofoveolatus, Rugulatisporitescaperatus, Gleicheniditessenonicus and Monocolpitesmarginatus (Van Hoeken-Klinkenberg, 1966; Germeraad et al., 1968; Umeji 2007; Chiaghanamet al., 2012), (See Figure 6).

Table 6 above shows the summary of palynomorphs percentage frequency distributions and their paleo-environmental inferences. The palynomorphs of environmental value encountered in the examined samples included, **Spinizonocolpites baculatus**, **Longapertites marginatus**, **Longapertites microfoveolatus** and **Laevigatosporitesovatus**.

The species of **Spinizonocolpites** and **Longapertites** are well-known pollen of palmae inhabiting similar environment as that of mangrove swamp of the humid tropics, (van der Hammen, 1954, van Hoeken-Klinkenberg, 1964, Muller, 1968, Umeji, 2002, Umeji and Nwajide, 2014, Ikegwuonu and Umeji, 2016). **Laevigatosporitesovatus** is a fern spore of swampy freshwater, (Rull, 1997 and Germeraad et al.1968).

In this study, there was a mixed condition of freshwater (non-brackish) forms in different proportions, with the brackish water/mangrove swamp species in the examined samples. The preponderance occurrence of **Longapertites marginatus** and **Spinizonocolpites baculatus** species, along with **Laevigatosporitesovatus**, in sample LOC 11, indicate deposition under near shore brackish water/or mangrove swamp environment, (Table 6).

Moreover, the presence of marine micro-plankton such as, **Spiniferites** sp. (open marine) and **Oligosphaeridium complex**, with corresponding absence of **Longapertites marginatus** and **Spinizonocolpites baculatus** (mangrove species), in samples LOC 5 and LOC 9, is indicative of open marine/shallow shelf depositional environment, (Table 6).

CONCLUSION

Integrating the results from geologic mapping, sieve analysis and palynological analysis, the study area is divided into three broad lithologic facie units: the lower sandy shale unit, which from palynomorphs analysis has been correlated to be of the same age with the Mamu Formation and its concluded to be belonging to the Mamu formation. This unit is overlain by the sandstone unit correlated to be the Ajali sandstone, which is overlain by the upper sandy shale unit correlated to be the Nsukka Formation. From the grain size distribution analysis, the sandstone unit is of a fluvial continental pale environment while palynomorph analysis revealed the lower sandy shale unit and the friable sandstone unit to be of a shallow marine paleoenvironment and the upper lateritic sandy-shale unit also revealed a mangrove swampy environment. Some data that were gotten from cross stratification pattern showed a mean vector azimuth of 244⁰ indicating Southwesterly paleocurrent direction and Northeastern provenance.

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